

CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTING TECHNICAL EDUCATION PROGRAMMES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the challenges encountered in the implementation of Technical Education Programmes in Secondary Schools within Akwa Ibom State. It delves into the concept of Technical Education, its developmental stages, the importance of technical education, and identifies key issues hindering its successful implementation in Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State. Additionally, the paper offers valuable recommendations to address these challenges.

Keywords: *Technical Education Programme, Challenges, Implementing.*

INTRODUCTION

Technical education programmes are an essential aspect of the schools' curricula in Nigeria, aimed at equipping students with practical skills to meet the demands of the country's evolving economy (Abaikpa *et al*, 2023). In Akwa Ibom State there are various types of schools that offer technical education, these schools which include; Technical Colleges, Vocational Schools, Polytechnic, Apprenticeship programs and Vocational centres, are designed to provide learners with practical, hands – on training in technical and vocational skills and equip them with the necessary skills to succeed in specific trades or Career. However, the implementation of these programs continues to pose significant challenges in the educational system. There are several factors that contribute to these challenges, including lack of infrastructure, inadequate funding, insufficient training of technical education teachers and limited access to modern technology and equipment. These obstacles do not only impede students learning but hinder the progress of the country's economic development, therefore addressing these challenges is crucial for the Government to achieve its vision of providing quality technical education and building a skilled and productive workforce, such that the aims and objective of the program is met.

CONCEPT OF TECHNICAL EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

The National Policy on Education defined technical education and vocational education as a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of the educational process involving in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life.

According to Ojimba (2013), technical education can be seen as the formal training of persons to become technicians in different occupations. Technical education in Nigeria has developed in response to the country's need for skilled and qualified personnel to support economic growth. Nigeria is an emerging economy with an expanding industrial base, and technical education has become essential for driving structural transformation, by providing a pool of skilled human resources necessary for advancing the nation's economy. Technical education is required to prepare students to be competent with their vocational interest which will lead to acquisition of practical as well as applied skills for basic scientific knowledge (NPE, 2013).

Daluba and Audu (2016) noted that Nigeria has been making series of efforts to keep pace with other developed nations of the world through her emphasis on science and technology, however the present situation of unemployment in Nigeria among technical educations graduates is an indication that the national objective for self-reliance has not been achieved, which is as a result of the gap that exist in the implementation of the program. The Nigerian government had made concerted effort to improve technical education across the country. Introductory technology equipment were imported into the country in the 1980's but were left in their crates and got looted, while the few that were installed were not functional. Also, various institutions had been established to offer broad range of courses and programs in technical education.

THE DEVELOPMENTAL STAGES OF TECHNICAL EDUCATION IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Technical Education in secondary schools in Nigeria has undergone several developmental stages since its introduction, which can be broadly categorized into the following:

1. **Pre-Colonial Era:** During this period, technical education in Nigeria was informal, with individual acquiring skills through apprenticeship and informal training skills such as blacksmithing, carpentry and crafting were passed down from generation to generation (Ojimba, 2012).
2. **Colonial Period:** The introduction of formal education by missionaries and colonial administrators marked the beginning of technical education in secondary schools. Vocational subjects like wood work, metal work and technical drawing were introduced in schools, with a focus on preparing students for specific trades (Egbo, 2005).
3. **Post-Independence Era:** (1960-1980): Following Nigeria's independence in 1960, the government emphasized the importance of technical education in secondary schools, leading to the establishment of more schools and the introduction of new subjects like electrical and mechanical engineering. However, the sector faced challenges such as inadequate funding and lack of qualified teachers (Nwachucwu,

2014).

4. **Structural Adjustment Period:** (1980-1990): This period was characterized by economic reforms and a shift towards a market driven economy. Technical education in secondary schools was negatively affected, with reduced funding and a decrease in the quality of instruction (Ibukun, 2015).
5. **Modern Era:** (1990- PRESENT): In recent years, there has been a renewed focus on technical education in secondary schools. With government and private sectors investing in infrastructure development (Saviour, Daniel, and Clement, 2024; Willie, Mboho and Udom, 2023), equipment provision and teacher training. Challenges like curriculum relevance and negative societal perceptions persist (Ojimba, 2012).

Technical Education in Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State has evolved significantly since the pre-colonial era. However, it continues to face challenges that must be addressed to ensure its effectiveness in providing skilled power for various industries.

THE IMPORTANCE OF TECHNICAL EDUCATION

Technical Education offers numerous benefits for students and society, these include

1. **Enhancing employability:** Technical Education equips students with job-specific skills that are in high demand across various industries (Rauner and Maclean, 2009). This makes them more employable and competitive in the job market.
2. **Promotion of entrepreneurship:** By developing hands-on, practice skills, technical education encourages entrepreneurship and innovation. Thus, graduates are more likely to start their own businesses, fostering economic growth and job creation. (Nagele and Stalder, 2018, Kingdom *et al*, 2024)
3. **Addressing skills gaps:** Traditional education often falls short in providing students with the specific skills required by many industries. Technical education bridges this gap by focusing on practical, job oriented training and entrepreneurship development (Pilot and Oliveira, 2019; Umanah *et al*, 2024).
4. **Increased earning potential:** With specialized skills and knowledge, technical education graduates often enjoy higher earning potential compared to those without technical training (Kuezera, 2017; Abaikpa, Thomas and Udom, 2022).
5. **Improved problem-solving abilities:** Technical education emphasizes critical thinking and problem – solving skills, enabling students to tackle real world challenges effectively (Rauner and Maclean, 2009).
6. **Adaptability in the Workplace:** The ever evolving nature of technology requires workers to be adaptable and open to continuous learning. Technical education prepares students to adapt to changes in their respective fields (Nagele and Stalder, 2008).
7. **Personal satisfaction and growth:** By acquiring practical skills and knowledge in their chosen fields, students experience a sense of accomplishment and personal growth (Rauner and Maclean, 2009). This can lead to increased job satisfaction and overall well-being.
8. **Socio-economic development:** A skilled workforce is crucial for the economic growth and development of any region or country. Technical education plays a vital role in providing the skilled labour required for various industries, leading to overall socio economic development (Kuezera, 2017).

CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING TECHNICAL EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN AKWA IBOM STATE

Technical education program in Akwa Ibom State is offered in various institutions. These institutions offer diverse programmes aimed at equipping students with practical skills and knowledge in various technical fields. However, its implementation has been plagued by several challenges that have hampered its effectiveness in producing competent graduates in secondary schools, these challenges include:

1. **Inadequate funding:** Technical education requires practical equipment, tools and infrastructure for effective teaching and learning. However, a greater percentage of Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State lack these resources. The inadequate funding of the program has resulted in dilapidated infrastructure, outdated equipment and poor learning environment in technical institutions (Ibukun, 2015). Due to lack of resources, students cannot access the necessary equipment to gain hands – on experience, which is essential for technical skills development.
2. **Outdated curriculum:** The curriculum in most technical institutions is outdated, failing to meet current industry needs and standards (Egbo, 2005). This has resulted in skills mismatch, where graduates of technical education may possess skills that do not match the requirements of current job markets, leading to high unemployment rates among graduates (Nwachukwu, 2014). Industries may struggle to find competent employees who can contribute effectively to their growth and development since technical education graduates lack the relevant skills and knowledge required by modern industries (Egbo, 2005). An outdated curriculum may hinder innovation in industries, as graduates are not equipped with the latest skills to drive advancements in their respective fields (Ibukun, 2015). Technical education curriculum in Akwa Ibom State falls in this description (Nkang and Umoh 2021).
3. **Lack of qualified teachers:** The shortage of qualified teachers with industry experience has adversely affected the quality of instruction in technical schools (Ibukun, 2015). The massive provision of introductory technology equipment by the Federal Government to Junior Secondary schools across the country including Akwa Ibom State in 1982 did not much help, because of the lack of qualified teachers to effectively handle those equipment. This posed a great challenge, Akwa Ibom State faces a shortage of skilled teachers, leading to suboptimal instruction (Umo, 2010).
4. **Negative societal perceptions:** Negative societal perceptions of technical program in Akwa Ibom State has resulted in low enrolment rates, where potential students are deterred from enrolling in the program (Nwachukwu, 2014). Technical education is frequently perceived as a last resort for students who perform poorly academically, leading to social stigma and discouraging potentially gifted students from pursuing this course. This misperception often results in the undervaluation of technical professions, potentially contributing to a shortage of skilled labour across various institutions.
5. **Limited asses to modern technology:** Modern technology plays a vital role in enhancing the quality and effectiveness of technical education program in secondary schools. However, limited access to modern technology poses a significant challenge in implementing these program in Akwa Ibom State, with several negative implications. Without access to modern technology, students may not receive adequate practical training, leading to a lack of hands – on experience and skills required by industries (Ojimba, 2013). According to Daluba and Audi (2016), limited access to modern

technology may prevent students from being exposed to the latest advances and innovations in various industries, which might lead to a gap between the curriculum and industry needs.

CONCLUSION

The current state of technical education in Akwa Ibom State is characterized by inadequate funding, outdated curricula, a shortage of qualified teachers and negative societal perceptions. To overcome these challenges, increased funding, curriculum review, teacher training and public awareness campaigns are recommended. By addressing these issues, technical education can contribute effectively to Nigeria's economic development by producing skilled manpower in various industries

RECOMMENDATION

To address these challenges, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Increased finding: The government should allocate more resources to technical education, prioritizing infrastructural development, equipment acquisition and teacher training.
2. Curriculum update: Curriculum should be reviewed regularly and updated. This should be done with stakeholders from industry to ensure that technical education aligns with industry needs. A curriculum review committee comprising educators, industry experts and government representatives should be established to look into the review and update the curriculum in line with current industry trends.
3. Teacher training and recruitment: Training programs should be implemented for existing teachers to enhance their skills, while qualified teachers with specialized knowledge in relevant fields are recruited. Secondary schools offering technical education should collaborate with educational institutions and industry partners to develop training programs that addresses the specific needs of Technical Education.
4. Promoting positive societal perceptions: Public awareness campaigns should be launched to promote technical education as a viable career path, highlighting the important role it plays in National Development.
5. To overcome the challenge of limited access to modern technology, there should be a public-private partnership to provide funding and resources for modern technology. Teachers should be trained and equipped with the skills and knowledge to effectively utilize modern technology in teaching. Collaboration with industry partners should be considered important to help provide access to modern technology and expose students to real-world applications.

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